

INTERACTIVE GAMES THAT IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH CLASS

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Abstract. Through this article, we present information that introduces interactive games that develop speaking skills of school-aged children, taking into account their interests and mental character.

Key words: EFL students, speaking skill, Bingo, Taboo, drawing activity, comic strip descriptions, debates, storytelling activity, two truth one lie, I have never.

ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ ИГРЫ, УЛУЧШАЮЩИЕ РАЗГОВОРНЫЕ НАВЫКИ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В данной статье мы представляем информацию, которая знакомит с интерактивными играми, развивающими речь детей школьного возраста с учетом их интересов и склада ума.

Ключевые слова: студенты EFL, навык говорения, бинго, табу, рисование, описание комиксов, дебаты, рассказывание историй, две правды и одна ложь, у меня никогда не было.

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Abstract. Through this article, we present information that introduces interactive games that develop speaking skills of school-aged children, taking into account their interests and mental character.

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the intellectual potential of children all over the world is developing dramatically under the influence of modern technologies and the Internet. The whole world is striving for renewal and growth. At the same time, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of reforms are being carried out to develop youth education and provide children with quality education that meets the latest requirements. In particular, we can give examples of the following decisions and laws issued on education: Resolution No. PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the activity of popularizing the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 312 dated 19.05.2021 "On measures for effective organization of promoting the learning of foreign languages".

In order to develop the aspect of speaking, teachers today use the direct method instead of using the grammar translation method. In this article, we will try to provide information about the direct method.

The Direct Method was established in the United States with Sauveur and Maximilian Berlitz throughout the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries in France and Germany. This approach emerged as a reaction to the grammar-translation approach's shortcomings. Its

developers contend that if instruction is focused on modeling and doing, a language may be taught without translation or the usage of the native tongue. It is preferable to actively use the language in class when teaching it as opposed to utilizing analytical techniques that center on delineating grammatical rules.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Language learnt in class should be used directly and spontaneously by students. This will enable kids to pick up the language and instill grammatical standards. By employing mime, presentations, and videos, one may teach new vocabulary using previously taught words.

Students are immersed in the target language in a similar manner to how they learnt their native languages. Its main goal is to have pupils ready to utilize the language for conversation. All language instruction is given verbally and in the language you desire to learn. The new vocabulary is taught by example and places a strong emphasis on speaking and listening, with proper pronunciation being given a lot of weight. The majority of the lesson period is devoted to oral practice.

English lessons are being deepened in schools on a large scale and using new modern interactive methods. In order to improve children's language skills, students use world-recognized and most widely used interactive methods. The main goal of developing language skills in children is to develop the ability to speak in them.

Forming a child to speak English freely requires the teacher to work hard and hard on the students. In this article, we will provide information on several speaking games that teachers can use in the classroom. Here are some of them:

BINGO: a present ideal and straightforward previous practice bingo game. Around the classroom, students pose "have you ever" inquiries about engaging subjects. Students write their names on the grid if they answer YES to any of the questions. The person with the most names on their paper is the winner. Following bingo, I asked my student select a question and the previous partner who had responded affirmatively. They requested information in the simple past.

TABOO: teachers arrange the pupils into four- or five-student groups. In the middle of each group, place a pile of cards with a random selection of nouns. Asking pupils to describe nouns for their group members to guess at turns. There is rivalry to see who has the most cards at the conclusion of the game since the group member who correctly guesses keeps the card.

DRAWING ACTIVITY: Students are paired off, and each is given a picture that is face down so that partners cannot view each other's cards. For their partner to sketch the picture, they must explain it.

COMIC STRIP DESCRIPTIONS: handle a section of a comic strip to each pupil. The pupils should make an effort to describe their images and organize the comic strip without first presenting their images to one another. The students can predict the sequence after around 10 minutes, check their answers with one another, and see whether they were right.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEBATES: Give every pupil a sheet of paper with the words "agree" and "disagree" printed on it. Each student should hold up their paper with the agree or disagree side based on their perspective while you read out a contentious statement. Pick a student from each side to present their argument and engage in a brief discussion.

SROTYTELLING ACTIVITY: Four pupils should be brought to the front of the room. One should stand behind them and serve as the controller while the other three should sit in a row. Hand a deck of cards with nouns inscribed on them to the controller.

TWO TRUTH ONE LIE: On a sheet of paper, each student should write three statements about themselves. One of them should be a falsehood, and the other two should be true. Students recite their three claims aloud while being questioned by their peers to attempt to ascertain which one is false.

I HAVE NEVER... Starting this exercise, each kid in the class should hold up five fingers (you can use less fingers to do this more quickly). The first-person speaker in the class shares one item they have never done. Students who have completed the task should raise their hands and share a story about it with the class. When all of a student's fingers are down, they are eliminated from the game.

CONCLUSION

Based on the school schedule, each lesson in classrooms lasts 45 minutes, and if almost 10 minutes of them are spent on repeating the topic, the teacher has only 35 minutes left, and the teacher can develop the child's language skills and not get bored in these 35 minutes. and uses new methods in order to constantly increase their attention to the lesson.

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